

D8.2: Branding

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ABSTRACT:	A project's communication and dissemination breadth, as well as impact are highly dependent on the quality of dissemination and communication tools and channels. A prerequisite for XR4HUMAN to achieve a successful conclusion are its products, i.e. reports, platforms, applications, etc, to be made visible in the best possible way. This is highly dependent on the types of relevant products to XR4HUMAN stakeholders. As a result, there is not one-size-fits-all strategy for appropriate dissemination and communication. This is why D8.2 cannot be understood in isolation from D8.1 or D1.1. This deliverable presents the branding of XR4HUMAN that aims at creating a distinct identity of the project's communication and dissemination channels, i.e., social media, website, and presentation templates. The main elements of the branding are the logo and the aesthetics that provide a uniform and aesthetically appealing look.
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1 Introduction

1.1 About the project

eXtended Reality (XR) technologies have within a few years moved from lab-based research to a common-place consumer item. Indeed, the benefits of and the possibilities that XR technologies offer to promote and enhance are prolific. As with other emerging technologies, however, the use and eventual ubiquity of XR technologies bring with them potential risks that have not existed before. Of particular importance are new ethical, and associated safety, privacy, security challenges and interoperability issues that needs to be considered now. Developing the foundations to ensure that Europe is sufficiently equipped to leverage these opportunities through skillful navigation of new challenges is the rationale for XR4HUMAN.

The MAIN OBJECTIVE of the project is to co-create living guidance on ethical and related policy, regulatory, governance, and interoperability issues of XR technologies within a European community of practice. This main objective will be operationalized through the following specific objectives:

- EXPLORE (i) ethical issues; and (ii) related regulatory and governance issues;
- GUIDE companies and regulators through (i) Interoperability Guidance Document; (ii) a European Code of Conduct for Equitable, Inclusive, and Human-Centered XR Technologies; (iii) recording and demonstrating the practical application of the XR Code of Conduct;
- EQUIP companies and regulators with an online repository of test cases to allow developers to demonstrate evidence of adherence to best practices;
- EQUIP and GUIDE users through a rating system and educational materials;
- ENGAGE companies and other stakeholders (i) to enhance the uptake of the XR Code of Conduct, the Guidance for Interoperability, and the empowerment of end-users; and (ii) to establish a permanent digital European Forum to facilitate stakeholder dialogue on issues of ethics and interoperability.

1.2 About this deliverable

XR4HUMANwork programme includes literature surveys and co-creation with groups of relevant stakeholders and potential end users. WP8 will provide visibility of the progress of the work and to the project's various outputs during the duration of XR4HUMAN; in such capacity WP8 will connect XR4HUMAN with relevant stakeholders and user communities, targeting at boosting uptake of project results. Considering that XR4HUMAN's dissemination and communication activities play a cardinal role in awareness-raising activities there is a strong need for the project to be backed by a powerful branding.

Main objective: This deliverable presents the branding of XR4HUMAN that aims at creating a distinct identity of the project's communication and dissemination channels, i.e. social media, website, and presentation templates.

2 XR4HUMAN branding

2.1. XR4HUMAN logo

The XR4HUMAN logo is depicted in Figure 1 and it will be the main distinctive feature of the project. It will be the most substantive element of the project's dissemination and communication activities.

Figure 1: The XR4HUMAN logo in vertical (left) and horizontal (right) orientations; the physical/real individual and her virtual counterpart separated by a digitized interface.

The project logo's main feature is the face of a person, bearing connotations of the concept of human-centered design that XR4HUMAN uses as a guiding principle. The "real" face of the person, the right one, has a counterpart, the left one, in the virtual world. The main distinction element between the "real" one and the "virtual" one is that the latter is pointed by the white pixel elements. These elements delineate the real and the virtual worlds by forming a diagonal separation feature. This feature can be considered as a boundary between the real and the virtual worlds, but it can also be seen as mirror that reflects the face of the real world into the virtual world. Variations of the project's logo are depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Variations of the XR4HUMAN logo.

2.2. XR4HUMAN colour palette

The colour palette of XR4HUMAN is presented in Figure 3. The difference in the area covered by each colour reflects, in a semi-quantitative way, the prominence these colors must have in all XR4HUMAN’s dissemination and communication channels. The colour palette has been tuned to reflect and produce the “mood” that the XR4HUMAN beneficiaries have chosen for the branding, that is: “High tech, Futuristic, Artificial Intelligence, People” (Figure 4).

This mood provides an environment that is mostly connected to high-tech applications. This “atmosphere” aims at producing a visual leitmotif that creates a sense of unity throughout the dissemination and communication channels of XR4HUMAN.

Figure 3: The colour palette of XR4HUMAN.

Figure 4: The moodboard of XR4HUMAN that creates a distinctive atmosphere.

2.3. XR4HUMAN typography

A successful selection and use of typography boosts brand personality and ensures clarity and harmony in all XR4HUMAN communications. Figure 5 depicts the typographic elements to be applied in all dissemination and communication activities of the project.

Exo

Barlow

Headlines

**ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz**

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Bodytext/subtitles

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

Figure 5: The typography of XR4HUMAN.

2.4. Combination of branding elements

Specific guidelines are going to be followed for the combination of the colour palette and typography. Figure 6 gives an overview of these guidelines that aim to provide a combination of optimal clarity of the text and a professional aesthetic result.

Figure 6: Combinations of colour and typography for an optimal result.

3 Applying XR4HUMAN branding

This section describes the application of the XR4HUMAN branding in the main dissemination and communication channels of the project, like the social media, website, as well as powerpoint and deliverable templates.

3.1 XR4HUMAN website

The XR4HUMAN website, upon its launch, will have the domain name XR4HUMAN.eu. It is going to act as the focal point of the project’s online dissemination channels, i.e., Twitter and LinkedIn. More specifically, the project’s social media pages will be easily reachable through the website’s front page. The design of the website was created during the first two months of the project, in collaboration with the coordinating team. XR4HUMAN website is going to be launched within February 2023. Below, we present a series of screenshots from the mockups of the project's website.

Figure 7: This will be the upper part of the website's front page. It contains the most concise form of information about XR4HUMAN.

Figure 8: This will be featured below the upper part of the front page and will contain more details (but still high-level) information about XR4HUMAN.

Figure 9: This part of the front page will contain information about the objectives of XR4HUMAN. During the initial phase of the project, it will be featured below the element depicted in Figure 8; later, as the first outputs of XR4HUMAN will have been developed it will find a place lower at the front page.

Figure 10: This part of the front page will contain, at the beginning, some basic description of XR4HUMAN's main outputs. At a later stage, this will be featured high on the front page, since it will display the most important elements relevant for the exploitation and impact of the project's outputs.

Figure 11: Here, the visitor will be able to find the main challenges XR4HUMAN is bound to address

Figure 12: The XR4HUMAN consortium is aware that the European audience may not be fully aware of the implications XR applications bring with their use. This part of the website will explicate in a simple language a number of concepts that are necessary for the work of XR4HUMAN to be understandable from the wide audience.

Figure 13: A separate part of the front page will feature the most important stakeholders and the most relevant exploitation pathways of XR4HUMAN outputs per stakeholder type.

Figure 14: At the bottom of the front page a contact form has been placed, together with the acknowledgement to our funders.

The above screenshots depict the initial version of the XR4HUMAN website. As the project becomes more mature, the progress and results will be featured in specifically-designed sections. As a result, the website will go through a series of updates, so as to reflect the progress of the XR4HUMAN empirical programme.

3.2 XR4HUMAN social media

The social media channels will initially be Twitter and LinkedIn. Twitter is going to be utilised for both dissemination and communication purposes, while LinkedIn is going to be utilised for dissemination purposes. Despite the fact that both platforms do not provide enough flexibility for substantive branding, WP8 leaders have used all available means to customise the mood in both cases. Figure 15 presents the application of XR4HUMAN branding in Twitter (left) and LinkedIn (right). The use and choice of specific social media platforms will be monitored on a continuous basis throughout the project, as to examine the adequacy and capacities of the platforms to reach the project's objectives.

Figure 15: XR4HUMAN branding as applied to Twitter (left) and LinkedIn (right) social media platforms.

XR4HUMAN website is going to be hosted in NTUA's server and it will be maintained there for three years after the end of the project, as described at the Grant Agreement. In addition XR4HUMAN's social media channels will stay active for the same duration of time after the end of the project.

3.3 XR4HUMAN power point template

Figure 16 presents the power point template of XR4HUMAN. This template is important, since all presentations on XR4HUMAN (e.g. conferences, workshops, cluster meeting dissemination events, engagement events, public communication events) will be based on those specific slides

Figure 16: XR4MUMAN branding as applied to the powerpoint presentation.

3.4 XR4HUMAN deliverable template

Figure 17 presents the deliverable template of XR4HUMAN. Special emphasis has been put not only at providing a placeholder for all needed information, but also to produce an aesthetically appealing result, since almost all XR4HUMAN deliverables are public. In this respect they are not going to play the role of purely technical reports, but also of an additional means of dissemination and communication.

Figure 17: XR4HUMAN branding, as applied to the deliverable template.

4 Next steps

The NTUA team, after the launch of the website, will start augmenting its content. Below there is a list of action points that are going to be applied within the first four months of 2023:

- Create a “Meet out Team” section, where structured information on all consortium members (individuals) are going to be featured
- Get in touch with the curators of the [Embassy of Good Science](#) platform. This is a platform that acts as a hub for the results of EU-funded projects, mostly Coordination and Support Actions, that deal with Research Ethics and Research Integrity-related challenges. The first aim is to create, at the [Initiatives](#) part [Community section](#), a placeholder for some baseline information of XR4HUMAN. As progress will be made XR4HUMAN deliverables are going to be featured at the Repository part of the Initiatives section.

5 Deviations from DoA

No deviations from the DoA.